

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

BIODIVERSITY INTERDEPENDENCIES WITH ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC INDICATORS

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Authors	Nelson Kevin Sinisterra-Solís, Sibylle Rouet-Pollakis, Neus Escobar, David Leclère, Neus Sanjuán

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0. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Agricultural production is associated with land use change, greenhouse gas emissions, and other environmental degradation, which, in turn, are drivers of biodiversity loss. Most of these effects are exacerbated by increasing agri-food exports, causing the displacement of environmental and socioeconomic pressures throughout supply chains. To understand these interdependencies, quantitative assessments benefit from the combination of both detailed trade data and sub-national environmental and socioeconomic indicators assessed using a life cycle approach. In Deliverable D6.3, we developed a bottom-up life cycle assessment (LCA) framework based on regionalized supply chain data and impact assessment methods to derive spatially-explicit indicators of biodiversity loss embodied in Brazilian soybean exports and derivatives to the EU. In addition, a new set of indicators for biodiversity impacts was derived for South America and Africa and implemented in the GLOBIOM modeling framework to derive biodiversity loss trajectories under alternative Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) until 2050.

This deliverable (D6.4) aims to derive quantitative indicators on agricultural commodity exports' environmental and socioeconomic impacts by combining detailed trade data and LCA approaches. The indicators assess the interdependencies between biodiversity loss and other sustainability dimensions along the supply chain. Specifically, a dedicated case study on Brazilian soy supply chains arriving in the EU in 2022 has been developed using one ton of soy equivalent arriving in the importing EU countries and the total amount of soy equivalents traded as reference units. To this aim, the supply chains' biodiversity, carbon, and water footprints, and four socioeconomic indicators are estimated: eco-efficiency, land deforestation footprint, soybean export dependence ratio, and impact on human health. The selected indicators are closely aligned with several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDGs 2, 3, 6, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 15, and 17, reflecting the interconnected nature of environmental sustainability, economic development, and human well-being. The case study of Brazilian soy supply chains in the year 2022 allows the main drivers of the environmental impacts to be identified, namely the demand for land resources (i.e., land transformation and occupation) in the biodiversity footprint, and the farming stage, specifically the production of fertilizers, in the carbon and water footprints. In addition, the producing states and the importing EU countries with the highest environmental footprint have been highlighted. As for the socioeconomic indicators, the eco-efficiency of the carbon footprint per USD-FOB¹ showed that the most eco-efficient municipalities are also those with the lowest carbon footprint and relatively low production, namely the ones located in Roraima, Tocantins, and Santa Catarina. The most eco-efficient municipalities in terms of biodiversity footprint are in Mato Grosso, Bahia, and Goiás, which are the states that cause a relatively low biodiversity loss per ton of soy-eq. and are among the primary producers of soy commodities generating higher revenues.

The intense deforestation induced by soy crops is reflected in the greater scores for the municipalities located in states such as Roraima, Rio Grande do Sul, and Maranhão. The soybean export dependence ratio shows that municipalities in Pará, Mato Grosso, and Matopiba region

¹ Soybean export value at the point of shipment

(Maranhão, Tocantins, Piauí, and Bahia) are the most export-oriented. The interdependency of the biodiversity footprint and the other indicators has also been analyzed. Along these lines, from the producers' perspective, it was observed that a large biodiversity footprint is not always associated with a large deforestation area, as it depends on the prevalence of land transformation vs. land occupation. Since the production and application of fertilizers are the main contributors to the carbon and water footprints and human health impacts, the three indicators are positively correlated in these states in the Centre-West, which are leading soy-producing states with high processing capacities. Differences across states in the average FOB price are minor since soy is an international commodity whose prices tend to be rather similar across the states, and differences are explained by the volume and the type of commodities exported. From the perspective of importing countries, analyzing the interdependencies across the indicators is more complex since it depends on the different producing municipalities from which it is sourced. Nevertheless, Belgium, Ireland, and Spain exhibit lower impacts on environmental footprints and socioeconomic indicators, whereas Germany shows less favorable results, being the country with most impactful marginal carbon footprint performance and one with the largest biodiversity footprint per ton of imported soy

To enable the analysis of long-term impacts and trade-offs under future scenarios, considering land use change and trade dynamics, the GLOBIOM modeling framework is used in WP7 to generate scenario-specific socio-economic and environmental indicators. These indicators were presented and illustrated in this deliverable for various socioeconomic dimensions (e.g., from food security to producer economic activity) and actors (e.g., producers vs consumers) at various spatial scales (continental scales globally, and national- to state-level for Brazil), as well as for multiple environmental impacts (climate change, resource use, pollution, biodiversity loss) at these spatial scales. These indicators make use of existing GLOBIOM indicators and rely on similar methods than mobilized for LCA for biodiversity impacts related to agricultural production explicitly modelled (see Deliverable D6.3). In this deliverable, we extended further the integration of LCA methods in GLOBIOM to also include biodiversity impacts related to upstream (e.g., fertilizer production) and downstream activities (e.g., domestic and international transport) for exported soy production, whose impacts are not explicitly modelled in GLOBIOM. The analysis of the biodiversity impact of the agriculture and forestry sector for 2020 and future scenarios in GLOBIOM revealed that globally, land stress is the primary driver of impacts on terrestrial ecosystems, while water stress dominates the impacts on aquatic ecosystems. The study also shows significant variations in impacts across regions and even within countries, with a more contrasted ranking of pressures. The study highlights the impact of omitting biodiversity impacts from upstream and downstream supply chain steps in the context of soy exports from Brazil, and the potential limits of the methods mobilized to account for those, such as assuming constant characterization factors. A comparison of biodiversity impacts of 2020 estimates from both the LCA and the GLOBIOM approaches allows an understanding of sources for deviations across estimates.

1. INTRODUCTION

Human activities are linked to the constant decline of global biodiversity through multiple mechanisms, including habitat reduction and fragmentation, natural resource exploitation, direct species depletion, environmental degradation, and climate change, among others (IPBES, 2019; Jaureguiberry et al., 2022). These multiple drivers occur simultaneously and at different scales, making it difficult to assess the causal responses undermining ecosystems' health as the positive or negative impacts of specific interventions (Geldmann et al., 2021; Isbell et al., 2023). As a land- and resource-intensive activity, agricultural production contributes to terrestrial and aquatic biodiversity loss. On the one hand, the direct land occupation (related to LU) and transformation (i.e., LUC from primary habitat) from primary ecosystems directly cause habitat reduction and fragmentation (Andersson et al., 2021; Haddad et al., 2015); on the other hand, the use of abiotic and biotic resources and the emissions associated with agricultural inputs indirectly reduce biodiversity by altering ecosystems' functions and biogeochemical cycles (Gibbs et al., 2009; Sigmund et al., 2023). Climate change poses additional risks and may act as a catalyst for biodiversity decline in certain latitudes (Scherer, Boom, et al., 2023; Warren et al., 2013).

To understand the biodiversity impacts of agricultural production, it is important to consider the effects and trade-offs of both intensification (through environmental pollution and resource extraction) and extensification (through land use change, LUC). Most of these effects are driven by the international demand for agri-food commodities, causing the displacement of environmental and socioeconomic pressures throughout supply chains (Chaudhary & Brooks, 2019; Hoang et al., 2023; Lenzen et al., 2012). To understand these interdependencies, quantitative assessments benefit from the combination of both detailed trade data and regionalized environmental and socioeconomic indicators. Life cycle assessment (LCA) provides a systematic framework to assess impacts associated with the consumption of resources (including land and water) and the emissions generated by production systems. Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) methods exist to translate these environmental pressures into impacts, either at the midpoint or endpoint level, using the so-called characterization factors (CFs). While midpoint indicators are considered intermediate measures of environmental impacts from emissions or resource use in the cause-effect chain (e.g., global warming, water scarcity), endpoint indicators are final measures of environmental impacts that reflect the damage or benefit to human health, natural resources, and ecosystems. Several CFs have been proposed to quantify the direct impacts of land occupation and land transformation, mainly in terms of species richness at the midpoint level (Chaudhary & Brooks, 2018; De Baan et al., 2013; Scherer, Rosa, et al., 2023). Available LCIA methods can also be used to quantify indirect impacts from environmental pressures on biodiversity within the area of environmental health protection (Sanyé-Mengual et al., 2022; Verones et al., 2020).

In Deliverable D6.3, we developed a bottom-up LCA framework based on regionalized supply chain data and available LCIA methods to derive spatially-explicit indicators of biodiversity loss (as potentially disappeared fraction of species integrated over the time, PDF·yr) embodied in Brazilian exports of soybean and derivatives to the EU. The indicators quantified biodiversity footprints of the commodities of interest by considering both land-use-driven and downstream

pollution-driven biodiversity loss (as PDF-yr per ton of soy equivalent), using fine-scale data on global imports and exports, agricultural expansion, and LUC over time. A new set of CFs for biodiversity impacts from land occupation and transformation was derived for South America and Africa. These were implemented in the GLOBIOM modeling framework to derive biodiversity loss trajectories under alternative Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) until 2050. Additionally, endpoint indicators from the LCIA method LC IMPACT (Verones et al., 2020) were included to understand the effects of other environmental pressures besides land stress (water stress, climate change, etc.) in terms of PDF-yr. Although biodiversity impact results in D6.3 also embedded the calculation of environmental pressures as indirect drivers in the cause-effect chain, trade-offs between environmental impacts, socioeconomic aspects, and species richness loss were not explicitly addressed. Given the complexity and scale of the impacts on biodiversity and its drivers, assessing sustainability trade-offs under both attributional and consequential LCA approaches is crucial to understanding challenges in the context of the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

2. OBJECTIVES

CLEVER investigates how international trade in agricultural and forest products drives biodiversity impacts through biomass supply chains and what the main biodiversity loss hotspots are in major producing and exporting countries. The final goal is to develop solutions for more sustainable production and consumption of agricultural and forestry commodities to support decision-making in collaboration with policy stakeholders, the private sector, and civil society. Although the focus is the study of biodiversity impacts associated with international demand for non-food biomass, particularly in the EU, other impacts and socioeconomic aspects should be considered to assess the sustainability of trade flows and supply chains.

This deliverable (D6.4) aims to derive quantitative indicators on the environmental and socioeconomic impacts of agricultural commodity exports by combining detailed trade data and LCA approaches. The indicators assess trade-offs between biodiversity loss and other sustainability dimensions along the whole supply chain. The indicators are subsequently integrated into the global modeling framework GLOBIOM for the analysis of long-term impacts and trade-offs from exogenous interventions, considering LUC and trade dynamics. D6.4 fulfills the following objectives:

1. To quantify environmental footprints and socioeconomic performance indicators of imports of soybean derivatives into the EU and assess trade-offs.
2. To include LCA-derived environmental impact indicators from 1) in GLOBIOM by considering soybean production at the municipal level in Brazil and simulated trade dynamics.
3. To derive long-term projections and trade-offs of environmental, socioeconomic, and biodiversity loss impacts from agricultural and forest activities with the extended GLOBIOM model by considering land use dynamics in the SSPs framework.

With this, D6.4 contributes to the following general objectives of the project and innovation, as described at the DoA:

- Objective I: **Improve our understanding of how biomass trade is linked to biodiversity outcomes and co-benefits in exporting and importing regions.**

- Objective III: (to provide evidence for) **Co-design concepts and value propositions for innovative interventions that exploit leverage points enabled by improved value chain knowledge** -considering trade-offs.
- Innovation 1: CLEVER quantifies past and simulated future impacts of trade in soy, forest products, and fishmeal/oil in high-value biodiversity areas by pioneering combinations of data-driven spatial and economic models.

3. METHODS

3.1. Estimation of environmental and socioeconomic impacts of Brazilian soy exports

This study applies an attributional LCA approach (ISO, 2006a, 2006b, 2017) to assess the environmental impacts of exports of soybeans and derivatives from Brazil to the European Union (EU27). This is one of the most internationally traded commodities in the world and one of the key products in CLEVER. The results are estimated based on the volume of soybean, cake, and oil exported annually in 2004-2022, considering the municipality of origin, the export route, and the country of destination. The functional unit (FU) is the mass of soy commodities traded. In this respect, two reference flows are used, the total quantity traded per supply chain from the origin (Brazil) to the EU and one ton of soybean equivalent (soy-eq.). This is defined as the quantity of raw soybeans embedded in the oil, cake, and bean flows that are ultimately generated at the end of each supply chain. It allows for comparing the different life cycles irrespective of the product imported. In this deliverable, only results for 2022 are shown as the last year in the period.

3.1.1. System description

Impacts are quantified ‘from cradle to factory gate,’ starting with land transformation into soybean farming up to the stage in which soybeans and derived products are delivered to the countries of import. Hence, the system boundaries include the sub-stages shown in Figure 1: land transformation (LUC), land occupation (LU), soybean farming, domestic transport, international maritime transport, and soybean crushing into oil and cake. The latter can occur either in the import country or Brazil before export. The flow of soy-eq. results from the allocation of soybeans among derivatives (oil and cake) based on data on individual shipments leaving Brazilian ports, soy production in the corresponding municipalities, and the subsequent crushing and storage facilities. It is assumed that soybean crushing delivers soy cake and oil in proportions of 80% and 19%, respectively, accounting for losses (Escobar et al., 2020).

Each supply chain embedded in the soy export volume is characterized by the municipality where the crop is produced, the ports in Brazil from which soybeans and derivatives are exported, and the destination ports in the EU. This study's geographical scope covered 2,210 soy-producing municipalities in Brazil that produce soybeans or derivatives (cake and oil), shipped from 20 Brazilian ports to 23 importing EU countries from 2004 to 2022. For 2022, 3,009 supply chains were evaluated, which implied 579 municipalities where soy was farmed to later arrive in 14 EU countries. The supply chains are identified from the *Trase* platform (Trase, 2024),

which is based on the so-called Spatially Explicit Information on Production to Consumption System (SEI-PCS) model that tracks supply chains of biomass-based commodities at subnational scales (Lathuillière et al., 2022). In addition to *Trase*, other data sources are used to quantify emissions and resource consumption from cradle to factory gate, detailed in the sections below.

Figure 1. System analyzed for Brazilian soy commodities marketed to the European Union.

3.1.2. Life cycle inventories at the municipality level

At the beginning of the supply chain, habitat degradation and emissions from direct land use (LU) and LUC are included based on Scherer et al. et al. (2023) and the IPCC guidelines (IPCC 2006a,b,c; 2019a,b,c,d), respectively. LUC refers to land conversion from previous uses into crop production and LU to cropland remaining crop production, in this case, soybean. These land cover changes translate into existing natural habitat changes and carbon stocks (above and below-ground biomass, litter, dead wood, and soil), ultimately affecting the existing biodiversity and releasing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. These impacts are usually quantified as a one-time effect following land conversion. However, they may also account for carbon flows such as those from forest biomass burning if this happens with the observed LUC effects.

MapBiomias (MapBiomias, 2025a) are used to identify land use prior to soybean production, with a resolution of 0.3 degrees (300 m x 300 m). For each pixel in which there were soybean areas in a given year of the period “t,” the land use existing in the year “t-3” was considered the one being cleared for soybean production, assuming that this is the time that it takes for the crop to be established (Escobar et al., 2020). Based on the use in “t-3”, pixels were classified into land (habitat) occupation or land (habitat) transformation, depending on whether soy is observed in a pixel where there was previously a natural habitat or an anthropogenic use (i.e., soy or another temporal crop), respectively. The share of pixel areas under habitat transformation (LUC) and occupation (LU) was later applied to allocate the environmental pressures that translate into biodiversity loss at the municipal level.

Based on TIER 1 of IPCC guidelines, changes in carbon stocks in above-ground biomass and soil organic carbon (SOC) were considered in the assessment. In addition, carbon changes in litter and dead organic matter were only considered when the land cover in “t-3” was natural forest, assuming that the carbon in these pools is zero or negligible in other land cover types. In contrast, dead organic matter and litter were not considered for crop-to-crop transitions. The associated difference in carbon stocks is converted into CO₂eq. Additionally, non-CO₂ greenhouse gas emissions (CH₄, N₂O, and NO_x) from biomass burning were considered when, in the period “t-3”, the pixels with natural vegetation cover were linked to fire disturbances. This approach required Brazilian raster layers at a 30 m resolution as raw data for land cover (collection 9), soil carbon stocks in the first 30 cm of soil (collection 2 beta), and fire scars (collection 3) from Mapbiomas (MapBiomas, 2025b,c,d).

Besides LUC, agricultural emissions from soil preparation, nitrogen fertilizer application, and fuel combustion during on-field operations, as well as those from the production of agricultural inputs (i.e., seeds, soil correctors, fertilizers, phytosanitary products, and fuel), were used as inventory data to assess the impacts of the farming stage, from cradle to farm gate. Information on average farming practices at the state level² was obtained from LCA studies (Lehuger et al., 2009; Cavalett et al., 2009; 2010; da Silva et al., 2010; Mourad et al., 2011; de Alvarenga et al., 2012; Romanelli et al., 2012; Castanheira et al., 2013; 2015; Maciel et al., 2015; Raucci et al., 2015; Altamirano et al., 2016; Esteves et al., 2016; 2018; Cerri et al., 2017; Kamali et al., 2017; Matsuura et al., 2017; Knoope et al., 2019; Capaz et al., 2020; Brito et al., 2023; Lucas et al., 2023; Giusti et al., 2023). All of them represent rainfed soybean production with no-tillage practices. When inventory data for a specific state was unavailable, the average for the region (North, North-East, Centre-West, South-East, and South) was used. Fertilization and limestone application release CO₂ and N₂O emissions, estimated using IPCC's Tier 1 factor emissions (IPCC, 2019d). To estimate NH₃ and NO_x emissions, the Tier 1 emission factors of the European Environmental Agency (EMEP/EEA, 2019) are applied. Nitrate leaching and phosphorus emissions are not estimated due to the low mobility of phosphorus and the negative nitrogen and phosphorus balances in Brazilian soils (FAO, 2004; Lucas et al., 2023). On-field emissions from pesticide application are not considered because most pesticides are unspecified in the literature reviewed. Their contribution to the impact categories specified below (section 3.1.3) is expected to be minor. Machinery use (common to the previous activities) is also considered, translating into additional emissions from fuel combustion.

As to the processing stage, data on inputs inventory (fuel, hexane, water, electricity, natural gas, etc.) per FU were obtained from the same literature as the farming stage, and consumption at the country level was used for the impact calculations. Emissions from fuel combustion for crushing were taken from the reference global process in Sphera software and database (Sphera, 2025). Data on emissions and resource consumption from energy and chemical inputs used in soy farming and processing were obtained from Ecoinvent v3.10, which were considered average for the state or region.

Finally, domestic and international transoceanic transport emissions were estimated by obtaining transport distances in each supply chain and multiplying them by the average

² This includes: Paraná (6 studies), Rio Grande do Sul (4), Mato Grosso (5), Goiás (2), Mato Grosso do Sul (5), Pará (1), Rondônia (1), São Paulo (2), Maranhão (1), Bahia (1), Minas Gerais (1); which correspond regions South (11), Centre-West (13), North (2), North-East (1), South-East (2), and Brazil (3).

impact/emissions per t-km from Ecoinvent v3.10 (Wernet et al., 2016). Transport distances were estimated using an optimization algorithm (cost minimization). For domestic transport, the ORS tool (HeiGIT, 2025) was used to estimate the distance between the supply and intermediate nodes based on realistic routes traveled by vehicles transporting heavy goods. Regarding international transoceanic transport, the distance between the intermediate and demand nodes was calculated through the Least Cost Path (FlowMap, 2022). From this algorithm, optimized lines were projected from the ports of origin in Brazil to the biggest freight port in each destination country. The algorithm avoids transit through land areas to approximate actual routes traveled by transoceanic vessels. The ORS tool and Least Cost Path were run through QGIS software, v3.34.0-Prizren (QGIS, 2024).

3.1.3. Filling data gaps and allocation procedures

Data imputation and allocation processes were conducted to align the input data with the goal and scope of the study, taking into account the units of analysis, the indicators to be estimated, and the characteristics of the production systems and reference units. It must be noted that *Trase* also includes trade flows for which either the municipality or the state of origin is unknown, or the country of destination is unknown. The first procedure involved imputing missing data to conveniently identify missing nodes (i.e., origin municipality, origin port, and destination country) to characterize the full supply chain, as well as the associated land use. Out of the 3,009 supply chains evaluated, 2,818 (93.6%) required no imputation for any variable, 141 (4.7%) required imputation for municipality identification, and 50 (1.7%) required imputation for both the origin municipality and the destination country. The procedure follows a deterministic and iterative data assignment based on retrospective analysis or proportional reasoning derived from soy-equivalent data.

The estimation of export flows of soybean derivatives as soy-eq. unit requires conveniently identifying how much of the soy input is allocated among the two derivatives. As mentioned above, soy-eq. integrates soybeans, soy meal, and soy oil with 1 ton of soy-eq. equivalent to 1.03 tons of soybeans (Lathuillière et al., 2022). While soybeans are the output of farming, crushing soybeans is required to produce soy meal and oil. Thus, the impact associated with the processing stage was allocated to each supply chain based on its share of the soy market between the origin municipality and the destination country for exported soy meal and oil. To achieve this, export data from the MDIC-Comex platform, detailing exports per municipality of origin and importer country, were used (MDIC-Comex Stat, 2024).

Another assumption was needed to represent double cropping practices at the municipality level. In Brazil, soy is often double-cropped with maize within the same year, depending on the season and the producing region. When this occurs, the inventory data on farming and farming practices and associated impacts must be properly allocated among the two crops. This was done based on the duration of the harvest cycle for soy and maize, respectively, throughout the year (Castanheira et al., 2015; Escobar et al., 2020). Since both crops occupy the land area for approximately the same number of months (i.e., between September/December and January/April for soy, and between January/March and June/July for maize), the impacts per ha were allocated 50%-50% to the two crops. This includes the area of transformed habitat, emissions from changes in carbon stocks and input consumption, and emissions related to soil

pH correction. The allocation was only applied to the share of soybean area that is double-cropped, based on statistics on harvested areas (IBGE-SIDRA, 2024). Double cropping was assessed in municipalities where the harvested area of the first maize season was smaller than that of the second, assuming that soy is produced before maize. Consequently, the double cropping surface area was estimated as the difference between the harvested areas of the second and first maize seasons. In contrast, the area under a single soy crop was determined as the difference between the total harvested area of soy crops and the double cropping area.

3.1.3. Environmental impact categories and impact intensity indicators

In D6.3, biodiversity impacts were assessed in terms of PDF time-integrated by combining midpoint CFs for species richness loss for land occupation and land transformation from Scherer et al. (2023) with endpoint CFs for damage to ecosystems quality from LC-IMPACT (Verones et al., 2020), with the latter referring to impacts on terrestrial biodiversity. These allowed for comparison with biodiversity impact results from GLOBIOM, which implemented endpoint CFs from LC-IMPACT, associated with several environmental pressures (see section 3.2.1). In this deliverable, the following indicators for environmental impact intensity per ton of soy-eq. are calculated:

- Biodiversity footprint, expressed as terrestrial biodiversity loss (PDF·yr/t soy-eq.), based on the impact assessment method from Scherer et al. (2023).
- Water footprint, based on the freshwater consumption method (m³ water/t soy-eq.) included in ReCiPe 2016 (Huijbregts et al., 2016)
- Carbon footprint, estimated with the climate change assessment method (t CO₂ eq./t soy-eq.) from ReCiPe 2016 (Huijbregts et al., 2016).

These indicators are aggregated at the municipality, state, and importing country level (depending on the supply chain stage) and subsequently linked to GLOBIOM variables, as indicated in Table 1.

Table 1. LCA-derived environmental impact intensity indicators across supply chain stages and associated level of aggregation to be implemented in GLOBIOM.

Aggregation level	Dimensions	Reference flows and indicators
Agricultural input production	Municipality (M), Destination country (C)	Quantities of soybean (t); CO ₂ eq. (t per t soy-eq.); Water eq. (m ³ per t soy-eq)
On-field N ₂ O emissions	Municipality (M), Destination country (C)	Quantities of soybean (t); CO ₂ eq. (t per t soy-eq.); Water eq. (m ³ per t soy-eq)

On-field CO ₂ emissions (machinery operations)	Municipality (M), Destination country (C)	Quantities of soybean (t); CO ₂ eq. (t per t soy-eq.); Water eq. (m ³ per t soy-eq)
Energy consumption in crushing	Municipality (M), Product (P), Destination country (C)	Quantities of soy-eq. (t) crushed into each product (P); Quantities of each co-product obtained (P); CO ₂ eq (t per t soy-eq.); Water eq (m ³ per t soy-eq)
Domestic transport	Municipality (M), Product (P), Destination country (C)	Quantities of soy derivatives transported (t); CO ₂ eq (t per t soy-eq.); Water eq. (m ³ per t soy-eq.)
Transoceanic transport	Municipality (M), Product (P), Destination country (C)	Quantities of soy derivatives transported (t); CO ₂ eq (t per t soy-eq); Water eq. (m ³ per t soy-eq.)

3.1.4. Socioeconomic impact indicators

In this deliverable, additional indicators are derived to measure the socioeconomic performance of the flows of soybeans and derivatives and, ultimately, the municipalities/states that export them or the countries that import them. More specific indicators on the social performance of specific supply chain stages (e.g., workforce intensity, child labor risk, revenues to smallholders, etc.) could not be included in the LCA since no data sources could be identified that consistently report these indicators at the desired level of spatial/temporal resolution for Brazil as a whole, i.e., for several municipalities and years.

- Eco-efficiency Ratio, or Environmental Impact Intensity per Revenue (EIIR). This indicator represents the environmental productivity of a product or service in economic terms. It is expressed as the impact embodied in soy exports or imports per unit of revenues generated, in this case, per export price (USD). To this aim, fresh-on-board (FOB) prices are used to compare the different exporting units, in this case, municipalities in Brazil. Prices are retrieved from *Trase* (Lathuillière et al., 2022) for 2022. This indicator is calculated for the carbon and biodiversity footprints (see section 3.1.3) at the producer municipality level. Higher values indicate greater environmental impact per USD generated, meaning that the economic activity is less environmentally efficient. Lower values suggest higher environmental efficiency, as less impact is generated per USD of revenue.

- Land Deforestation of Soy Imports. This indicator captures the deforestation (ha/t soy-eq) of countries importing soybean derivatives as the area of land cleared from non-anthropogenic uses (i.e., ha of land transformation or deforestation in the municipalities of origin according to the approach in section 3.1.2) to produce the soybean derivatives they imported in 2022. In other words, this captures the ha of deforested land embodied in the countries' imports (EU27), expressed per unit of soy-eq.

- Soybean Export Dependence Ratio. This indicator represents how export-oriented soybean production is in each municipality and state and captures the ratio of foreign consumption to total demand (including exports) of soy-eq. (%). This indicator is calculated for sourcing units (i.e., municipalities) and then aggregated at the state level.

- Human Health Impact. Human health impacts are considered social indicators because human health reflects environmental and living conditions, in the sense that high disease rates may indicate pollution, lack of resources, or unsafe living conditions. Moreover, environmental health is closely tied to public health, affecting disease prevalence and life expectancy. The indicator is estimated with the endpoint CFs "damage to human health" from LC-IMPACT (Verones et al., 2020), as disability-adjusted life years (DALYs). This indicator captures how many healthy years are lost due to a certain cause of premature death or a disability; in this case, the damage is caused by seven impact categories affecting human health, namely water stress, human toxicity, particulate matter formation, and photochemical ozone formation, climate change, stratospheric ozone depletion, and ionizing radiation. These are estimated per FU, as detailed in section 3.1.1.

3.2. Environmental and socioeconomic indicators in GLOBIOM

3.2.1 Linking LCA impact assessment methods to GLOBIOM for assessing beyond farm gate environmental impacts of Brazil soy production

In Deliverable D6.3, LC-IMPACT CFs (Verones et al., 2020) were integrated into GLOBIOM to calculate biodiversity impacts, expressed in PDF·yr. The CFs were linked to key environmental pressures from farm activities in GLOBIOM, including water consumption, phosphorus inputs, GHG emissions, and land occupation. Additionally, for South America and Africa, biodiversity impacts from land occupation and land transformation were assessed using spatially explicit characterization factors developed in Deliverable D2.4. This allowed for a detailed analysis of global and Brazilian contributions to biodiversity loss and the study of the relationship between agricultural intensification and biodiversity impact.

However, to fully assess the environmental footprint of the Brazilian soy supply chain, impacts beyond the farm gate must be included. The LCA approach described in section 3.1 was used to derive impact coefficients per ton of product and co-product, respectively, across the different supply chain stages. The coefficients are then integrated into GLOBIOM by linking them to key soy supply chain variables. To avoid double counting, only impacts not already covered in GLOBIOM are calculated using the LCA from section 3.1. Table 2 below summarises the linkage.

Table 2. Summary of the methodology used to link LCA coefficients developed in section 3.1 to GLOBIOM while avoiding double counting.

Supply chain step	Climate change	Water	Other impacts	LCA coefficients	GLOBIOM Variable
Inputs to farming	LCA	LCA	Not assessed	Impacts per ton of Soy produced at municipality level	Quantities of soy produced at 30 arcmin grid
Farming	GLOBIOM /LCA	GLOBIOM	GLOBIOM	Impacts per ton of Soy produced at municipality level	Quantities of soy produced at 30 arcmin grid
Crushing	LCA	LCA	Not assessed	Impacts per ton of Soy or soy derivative produced at municipality level	Soy oil and Soy cake, output of the processing step – at the <i>Country</i> level, downscaled to 30arcmin grid based on <i>Trase</i> combined with Comex-Stat.
Domestic and Foreign transportation	LCA	LCA	Not assessed	Impacts per ton of Soy or Soy derivatives traded between the municipality and import country	Soy, Soy cake, and Soy oil traded – at the <i>Country</i> level and region of destination, downscaled to 30arcmin grid based on <i>Trase</i> combined with Comex-Stat.

The LCA presented in Section 3.1 calculated impact coefficients per ton of soy products for each supply chain step and from municipality to destination region, covering different years (2005 to 2020). In GLOBIOM, we implemented midpoint coefficients for climate change and freshwater consumption, calculated using ReCiPe (“Climate change, default, excl. biogenic carbon” in kg CO₂eq. and “Freshwater Consumption” in m³) (Huijbregts et al, 2016). The selected midpoint indicators align closely with the climate change and freshwater consumption impacts already calculated in GLOBIOM, which allows us to combine the impacts from both LCA and GLOBIOM data.

The time series from Section 3.1 allows us to have specific impact coefficients for the years 2010 and 2020. For 2000, the coefficients for 2005 are applied (as the oldest available), and for years after 2020, the coefficients for 2020 are used. As a result, the impact will not change dynamically in response to potential reductions in input or emission intensity that could occur in specific scenarios.

While GLOBIOM already includes most farm-level impacts, the LCA provides additional climate change impacts, such as CO₂ emissions from limestone application and machinery use. Additionally, GLOBIOM does not typically cover the production of agricultural inputs, such as fertilizers and pesticides. To bridge this gap, the LCA approach described in Section 3.1 are used to estimate these environmental impacts. For both farming activities and input production, the impact coefficients per unit of soy produced are linked to soy production data in GLOBIOM. The municipality-level coefficients are linked to GLOBIOM grid-level data, based on the quantity of product produced in each municipality, derived from Trase (*Trase, 2024*), as calculated in section 3.1.3.

Deliverable D6.2 refined the GLOBIOM modeling of the soy supply chain by adding the crushing stage into the model. However, the impacts related to this step were still missing. Similarly, the impact of the transport of the traded soy products is missing in the model. The impact coefficients per ton of product and coproduct for crushing and transport have been, therefore, linked to the processed products and to the traded products between Brazil and the rest of the world, respectively. However, the traded amounts and the processed quantities in GLOBIOM are only calculated at the region level (Brazil). Thus, *Trase* data (*Trase, 2024*), combined with COMEX-STAT data (MDIC-Comex Stat, 2024) are used to estimate the subnational flows of soy and soy products between the different municipalities and the rest of the world. This means that the subnational distribution of the crushing and transport impacts is not directly linked to the distribution of soy production as estimated by GLOBIOM. This might result in some inconsistencies, especially when it comes to projections.

It must be noted that since the LCA in Section 3.1 focuses on the impacts of exported goods, domestic transportation for Brazilian consumption of soy products is not included in the estimations. The same happens with the impact of soy processing since only the crushing step in Brazil has been assessed in the LCA. This means that the impact coefficients are only linked to domestic processing in GLOBIOM, even if the processing takes place in other regions of the world, such as China or the USA (as shown in Deliverable D6.2). If the share of additional impact is relevant, this approach could be extended to include other processing regions and potentially additional crops, providing a more comprehensive assessment of supply chain impacts in the model.

3.2.2. Additional environmental and socioeconomic indicators in GLOBIOM for Brazil and the rest of the world

In addition to the LCA-derived indicators presented above, this deliverable produces projections of a range of socioeconomic indicators associated with agricultural markets using the GLOBIOM model. Unlike the impacts discussed in the previous section, the environmental impacts do not account for upstream (e.g., production of inputs like fertilizers) and downstream (e.g., transport, processing, etc.) activities. However, both environmental and socioeconomic indicators explicitly account for dynamically projected changes in markets (e.g., supply, trade, and demand physical flows and market prices at the commodity level), as well as in resource use (e.g., land and water use, land conversions), resource use efficiency (e.g., crop yields and irrigation water requirements) and impacts (e.g., GHG emissions from cropland and pasture soils, livestock and LUC) associated with production.

Environmental impacts

We focus on indicators reflecting changes in both emissions (e.g., land and water use, GHG emissions) and biodiversity impacts. This leads to four types of indicators:

- **Changes in land use:** The amount of land (in million ha) is reported under 4 categories of land uses (cropland, pasture, forest, and other land). Projected values reflect the initial land use and land cover for the year 2000 and explicitly simulated conversions between individual land uses at the subnational level (e.g., ca. 50 by 50 km in Brazil, coarser in the rest of the world – see D6.2) at each decadal time step, cumulated to the reported time horizon. The conversions reflect agricultural production changes in relation to regional agricultural market dynamics and LUC costs, subnational land endowments, and technological changes (e.g., long-term yield gains from research and development efforts, adoption of alternative endogenously modelled technologies like irrigation)
- **Changes in water use:** The amount of water withdrawn for irrigation (in km³) is reported. Projected values reflect the initial distribution of irrigated harvested area for the year 2000 and agricultural production changes in relation to regional agricultural market dynamics, subnational surface water, and groundwater endowments, and technological changes (e.g., long-term yield gains from research and development efforts, adoption of alternative endogenously modeled technologies like irrigation).
- **Changes in GHG emissions:** The amount of GHG emissions from agricultural activities (primarily N₂O emissions from cropland and pasture soils, and CH₄ from rice cultivation and enteric fermentation in ruminant animals) and LUC (CO₂ emissions) are reported as separate categories. Projected values reflect the initial distribution for the year 2000 and subsequent dynamics in agricultural activities, as well as crop and livestock management systems (that differ in emission intensity). Emissions from crop production, livestock production, and land use change are reported as separate categories.
- **Changes in biodiversity impacts from local production:** The amount of biodiversity loss from agricultural activities is reported in PDF-yr (Potentially Disappeared Fraction year). The projected values represent estimates of time-integrated future biodiversity impacts on freshwater and terrestrial ecosystems. It has been assessed using LC-IMPACT (Verones et al., 2020) for the following pressures on biodiversity: Climate change, Land occupation, Land transformation, Water stress, and Freshwater Eutrophication (see Method in D6.3).

Socioeconomic impacts

GLOBIOM quantifies different socioeconomic indicators that cover various supply chain steps, from production to consumption, as well as various groups of commodities: e.g., primary crop products with a distinction of soy vs other crops, secondary products – e.g., protein cakes and vegetable oils – and primary livestock products altogether. This deliverable specifically focuses on the following indicators:

- **Changes in food availability.** Food availability is a consumer-oriented metric and one of the components of food security (together with food access, utilization, and stability). It

represents the amount of food products available to the consumer in a country, including domestic supply and imports. We report it in per capita daily availability in terms of energy content (kilocalories per capita per day, kcal/c/d), with a split between plant-based and animal-based products.

- **Changes in production and net trade physical volumes.** Production and net trade (defined as the difference between exports and imports) are market balance indicators relevant to both production (e.g., amount of production and fate), trade (e.g., net trade balance), and consumption (e.g., the sum of production and net trade equals domestic consumption). They can be indicative of regions with export dependency for production (e.g., positive net trade representing a significant share of production), or import dependency for consumption (e.g., negative net trade representing a significant share of consumption). We report them in physical volumes (e.g. thousand tons of fresh matter), and we distinguish livestock final products from crop final products. Within crop final products, we further distinguish soy, other crops, soy protein meals, other cakes, soy oil, and other vegetable oils.
- **Changes in the value of production.** This metric is a production-oriented indicator, defined at the product level as the domestic production multiplied by the market price and aggregated across products. It complements the information on physical production volumes by integrating the impact of changes in market prices that relate to the scarcity of a product as demand and supply co-evolve. We report the value of production for various primary product aggregates: soy, other crops, and livestock products.

We explored the potential to produce additional socioeconomic indicators, such as the share of revenues to smallholders, forced labor, or child labor, available from the PSILCA database (Loubert et al., 2023) through the Ecoinvent database. This could, in theory, be achieved by coupling GLOBIOM production projections to related CFs from Ecoinvent, as done with LC-IMPACT CFs for environmental impacts. However, while the coupling to LC-IMPACT could be done through environmental pressures (e.g., land use, water use, nitrogen fertilizer use) and build on GLOBIOM dynamic representation of important determinants of the relationship between production and pressures (e.g., through changes in crop yield and water use efficiency), this was not possible for social indicators. A range of important factors shaping the dynamics of these indicators are not covered in GLOBIOM, and this coupling method was estimated as too unreliable for projecting those indicators up to 2050. The GLOBIOM model could potentially be improved to better represent aspects such as smallholder farming and farm revenue, but this would require resources and collaborations far beyond the scope of the CLEVER project.

Spatial resolution for indicator reporting

The indicators are calculated for different geographical entities that rely partly on community standards (e.g., AgMIP) for reporting and allow covering the whole world with differentiated levels of detail. We aggregated all these indicators from the original 37 GLOBIOM world regions in 5 global regions (aggregated AGMIP regions: Northern America NAM, Latin and Central America OAM, Africa, and Middle East AME, South Asia SAS, Rest of the world ROW) as well as

Brazil (BRA, a subset of OAM) and European Union (EUE, a subset of ROW) as single reporting regions. In addition, for all environmental indicators and physical production levels (primary products only, i.e., soy crop but neither soy protein meal nor soy oil), we aggregate the results from the highest spatial resolution in Brazil (ca 50 by 50 km grid) to the Federal States. Other socioeconomic indicators cannot be reported at this level because of a lack of subnational modeling of key variables such as demand, trade, processing, and prices.

3.2.4. Illustrative scenarios

The Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) scenario framework is applied to illustrate model projections of the selected environmental and socioeconomic indicators for 2020 and future (2020-2050) periods. As further detailed in D6.3, these scenarios provide narratives for the main drivers of global change (e.g., population, GDP, dietary preferences, trade, technological progress) commonly used in the global change literature (O'Neil et al., 2017; 2020) and have been extensively studied with global land use models like the GLOBIOM model (Fricko et al., 2017; Popp et al., 2017; Stehfest et al., 2019). Projections for the selected indicators were generated for the SSP2 (Middle of the Road) scenario, picturing a prolongation of historical trends.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Environmental footprints of Brazilian soybean imports into the EU

4.1.1. Biodiversity footprint

The total biodiversity footprint due to the 14.6 million tons of soy-equivalent marketed from Brazil to the EU in 2022 accounts for $2.34 \cdot 10^{-4}$ PDF·yr. This corresponds to $1.6 \cdot 10^{-11}$ PDF·yr per ton of soy-eq. at the country level. The relative contribution of each stage, as well as that of Brazilian states and EU countries, to the overall biodiversity impact of soybean exports, can be seen in Figure 2. The results show that the natural habitat transformation and the land occupation to grow soy contribute approximately 50% and 30% to the total impact, respectively. The remaining 20% is distributed among the other stages, with fertilizer production as the most significant source in the agricultural stage, and fuel production and combustion in the processing stage. Domestic and international transport has a minimal impact compared to the other assessed stages included.

The Sankey diagram also presents the results of Brazilian producing states and European importing countries at the beginning and the end of the export flows (Figure 2). The impact is expressed both for the total export volume (biodiversity flow width) from each state to each destination country, as well as per ton of marketed soy (legend color scale). As expected, the total biodiversity impact varies across Brazilian states depending on the volume of soy exported. From the producer perspective, Mato Grosso and Bahia, the largest exporters with 5,455,787 and 3,965,351 tons (64.5% of the market), account for a biodiversity impact of $6.49 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and $4.69 \cdot 10^{-5}$ PDF·yr, respectively, followed by Paraná and Rio Grande do Sul and Maranhão. However, from a marginal point of view, the impact ranges from $9.67 \cdot 10^{-12}$ to $4.94 \cdot 10^{-9}$ PDF·yr/t

soy-eq, with Roraima (Amazonia biome) being the state with the largest biodiversity footprint, much larger than those of Santa Catarina (Atlantic Forest biome), and Piauí, which are the second and third impacting states, respectively, followed by Paraná and Rio Grande do Sul. These states have the highest land resource demand (in ha) or are in the most biodiverse (species-rich) biomes.

Among European countries, France, Spain, and the Netherlands are the countries that import soybean derivatives in larger amounts, leading to the greatest biodiversity footprints in absolute terms, with values of $4.22 \cdot 10^{-5}$ PDF-yr, $4.73 \cdot 10^{-5}$ PDF-yr, and $4.45 \cdot 10^{-5}$ PDF-yr, respectively. Regardless of their market shares, the impacts of Spain and the Netherlands exceed those of France since the soy-eq. they import are farmed in states with a high marginal impact, such as Roraima. Overall, the marginal results at the country of destination level range from $1.19 \cdot 10^{-11}$ PDF-yr/t soy-eq. (Romania) to $3.32 \cdot 10^{-11}$ PDF-yr/t soy-eq. (Portugal). Portugal, Germany, and Slovenia are the countries with the largest footprint per ton of imported soy, followed by the Netherlands, Spain, and Ireland since the soy arriving in these countries is mainly farmed in the Brazilian states with the highest footprint per ton, as mentioned above. This explains that France, despite being one of the main soy importers in the EU, has a low biodiversity footprint per ton since soy is mainly farmed in Bahia, which has a low footprint per ton of soy-eq. It is worth noting that the soybean arriving in Portugal is mainly sourced from Roraima, and that Spain and the Netherlands are identified as hotspots not only because they are the first and the second biggest soy importers in EU27 but also because a great share of the imports comes from origins with a high marginal impact, namely Maranhão, Tocantins, and Amapá. Romania, Greece and Sweden show the lowest values, reflecting differences in sourcing patterns and supply chain characteristics.

Figure 2. Biodiversity footprint of soy commodities traded from Brazil to the European Union in the year 2022. Estimations using LC-IMPACT endpoint CFs, except for biodiversity loss from land use impact, which was estimated by Scherer et al. (2023).

4.1.2. Carbon footprint

The estimated carbon footprint of Brazilian soy exports to the EU in 2022 amounts to 28.24 million tons of CO₂-eq., equivalent to 1.94 t CO₂-eq./t soy-eq. Farming is the stage of the supply chain with the greatest contribution (60%), followed by processing (25%) and transport (15%) (Figure 3). Regarding farming, GHG emissions from fertilizer production and application are the main source of farming. In contrast, the changes in carbon stocks due to land transformation make a much smaller contribution. Domestic transport makes a greater contribution to the carbon footprint than international transport, which highlights the higher efficiency of the latter, that is, the lower GHG intensity per km.

From the producer perspective, it is expected the states with the highest production mentioned in section 4.1.1 also have the highest absolute carbon footprint, namely Mato Grosso (10.3 million tons CO₂-eq.), Bahia (7.8 million tons CO₂-eq.), and Paraná (3.8 million tons CO₂-eq.). The last two are also the states with the greatest marginal carbon footprint (1.97 and 3 t CO₂-eq./t soy-eq., respectively) together with Minas Gerais (2.1 t CO₂-eq./t soy-eq.) and Mato Grosso do Sul (1.92 t CO₂-eq./t soy-eq.). From the importer perspective, France, the Netherlands, and Spain are the importing countries associated with the largest carbon footprint in absolute terms. Opposite to the results of the terrestrial biodiversity loss, the Netherlands and Spain show a better performance than France in the marginal carbon footprint; consequently, although Spain has the second largest market share, it ranks third in terms of absolute carbon footprint impact. Among all EU countries, Germany (2.4 t CO₂-eq./t soy-eq.), Poland (2.2 t CO₂-eq./t soy-eq.) and Sweden (2.1 t CO₂-eq./t soy-eq.) exhibit the most impactful marginal performance, whereas Portugal, Spain, and Ireland are the ones with the lowest marginal carbon footprint, with 1.65 t CO₂-eq./t soy-eq., 1.69 t CO₂-eq. t soy-eq. and 1.72 t CO₂-eq./t soy-eq., respectively.

Figure 3. Carbon footprint of soy commodities traded from Brazil to the European Union in the year 2022.

4.1.3. Water footprint

The estimation of the water footprint of the soybean imported to the EU in 2022 yields 198.5 million m³ of freshwater, around 13.6 m³/t soy-eq. Despite being a rainfed crop, the farming stage has the most significant contribution (Figure 4), mainly because of fertilizer production, followed by soybean processing and domestic transport. As expected, the states with the greatest water footprint are the leading producers (Mato Grosso, Bahia, and Paraná). However, freshwater consumption per ton of soy-eq. exhibits greater variability across states compared to biodiversity and carbon footprint indicators. Paraná, Pará, and Minas Gerais states have the highest marginal water footprint, with values of 21.5, 16.8, and 15.3 m³/t soy-eq., respectively, followed by Bahia, Goiás, Maranhão, Mato Grosso, and Mato Grosso do Sul, with scores ranging from 13.15 to 14.5 m³/t soy-eq. Rio Grande do Sul and São Paulo have the lowest values, namely 11.35 and 10 m³/t soy-eq., respectively. The six remaining states, shown in Figure 4, form the group with the lowest impact, with freshwater consumption ranging between 2.8 and 3.9 m³/t soy-eq.

When looking at the importing countries, the largest water footprints correspond to those that import soy derivatives in larger quantities (France, Netherlands, and Spain). Marginal water footprint results are more homogeneous, ranging from 11.93 m³/t soy-eq. for Portugal to 16.86 m³/t soy-eq. for Germany, which exhibits the highest value. Other countries with high marginal footprint are Poland and Denmark, followed by Sweden, France and the Netherlands. In the case of Germany, most of the imports come from Paraná, which is among the states with the highest marginal water footprint; however, Spain, one of the leading importers, has a relatively low marginal water footprint because it is mainly supplied from Mato Grosso, with a middle-high marginal footprint, and from other states with a relatively low water footprint.

Figure 4. Water footprint of soy commodities traded from Brazil to the European Union in 2022.

4.2 Socioeconomic impact results

4.2.1. Human health

The impact on human health caused by the soybean supply chains (Figure 5) is measured in Disability-Adjusted Life Years (DALYs) and for the Brazilian soy-eq. marketed to the EU in 2022, it accounts for 93,456 DALYs. It is mainly associated with farming practices, in particular, due to the production of farming inputs and the associated on-field emissions. In contrast, the contribution from soybean processing, domestic transport, and international transport is relatively similar. Like in the case of freshwater consumption, Mato Grosso, Bahia, Paraná, and Goiás are the states with the highest absolute impact on human health. Notably, Paraná, Bahia, and Minas Gerais make up the group of states with the highest marginal impact (between $6.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $9.64 \cdot 10^{-3}$ DALY/t soy-eq.). Ceará, Distrito Federal, Piauí, Roraima, Santa Catarina, and Tocantins show the lowest impact on human health, around $2.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ DALY/t soy-eq.

From the EU perspective, France (3.02 million tons soy-eq.) and Germany (1.4 million tons soy-eq.), two of the four leading soybean importers, are also the importing countries with the main marginal impact on human health, together with Poland. For instance, most of France's imports come from Bahia, which is among the states with the highest impact on human health, and the soybeans arriving in Germany are mainly sourced from Bahia and Paraná.

Figure 5. Impact on the human health (DALY) of soy commodities traded from Brazil to the European Union in 2022. Estimations using LC-IMPACT endpoint CFs.

4.2.2. Eco-efficiency ratio

The results of the eco-efficiency indicator considering the climate change impact per USD-FOB (Figure 6a) show that the most eco-efficient municipalities, that is, those with the lowest ratio (<3.4 CO₂eq/USD-FOB), are also those with the lowest carbon footprint intensity (see Figure 3). These have, in turn, a relatively low production, namely the ones located in Roraima (RR), Tocantins (TO), and Santa Catarina (SC). On the other hand, municipalities in Paraná (PR) stand out as the least eco-efficient, followed by Mato Grosso do Sul (MS) and Minas Gerais (MG), which can be explained by their high carbon footprint intensity, as commented in Section 4.1.2.

When analyzing the eco-efficiency of the biodiversity footprint (Figure 6b), the most eco-efficient municipalities in terms of biodiversity footprint (<2.4 10⁻¹⁴ PDF ·yr / USD-FOB) are in Mato Grosso (MT), Bahia (BA), and Goiás (GO), which are the states that cause a relatively low biodiversity loss per ton of soy-eq. and are among the primary producers of soy commodities and, therefore, generate higher revenues from their soy exports. Paraná (PA) is also eco-efficient despite having some municipalities with relatively low eco-efficiency. Roraima (RR) municipalities stand out because of their low biodiversity eco-efficiency despite exhibiting the highest carbon eco-efficiency index, which shows a trade-off. This is explained by the large biodiversity footprint of the soy-producing municipalities in this state, which is associated with the high deforestation observed in the analyzed period. Along these lines, it is also worth mentioning the low eco-efficiency of municipalities in Santa Catarina (SC), Rio Grande do Sul (RS), and Maranhão (MA).

Figure 6. Eco-efficiency ratios as climate change (a) and terrestrial biodiversity footprint (b) per USD of soy commodities traded from Brazil to the European Union in 2022.

4.2.3. Land Deforestation Footprint of Soy Imports

The results of the deforestation intensity in the soy-producing municipalities associated with each EU importing country in the year studied are represented in box and whisker plots and have been classified into six groups according to the percentiles of the deforestation ratio (Figure 7). It can be observed that the deforestation ratio of most of the municipalities (507 out of 579) is lower than 0.1 ha/t soy-eq. (the three diagrams above in Figure 7). Among the remaining municipalities, 65 show a high deforestation indicator between 0.1 and 5.2 ha/t soy-eq., and only 7 municipalities show very high deforestation (between 10 and 30.5 deforested hectares per ton of soy-eq.). These export soy commodities to Spain (ESP), Portugal (PRT), and the Netherlands (NDL). As indicated above, after France, Spain and the Netherlands are the top soy commodity importers in the EU, making them more likely to also source from new producing municipalities where there has been recent deforestation to meet their demand. Portugal's imports are much lower but mainly sourced from recently deforested areas (mainly in Roraima state), which also explains the high marginal biodiversity footprint, as commented in section 4.1.3. The reasons behind these trade relationships could be better explained by looking at the specific traders involved in soybean export flows.

Figure 7. Import intensity of high-deforestation soybean derivatives expressed as hectares deforested in soy-producing municipalities per ton of soy-equivalent imported in each EU country.

4.2.4. Soybean Export Dependence Ratio

The soybean export dependence ratio shows that municipalities in Pará, Mato Grosso, and Matopiba region are the most export-oriented (Figure 8). However, while Mato Grosso is the largest soy-producing state – where soybean crops expanded dramatically in the last decades driven by technological advancements – some of its municipalities show a relatively lower foreign demand. Unlike Pará and Matopiba, which are considered the current deforestation frontiers and where most soy production in 2022 was driven by international demand, the southern states follow a different pattern. In the South, nearly 100% of soybean production in 2022 was allocated to the domestic market. Traditional agricultural states like Santa Catarina maintain a more stable agricultural commodity market, with less reliance on exports.

Figure 8. Soybean export dependence ratio

4.3. Interdependency of soybean biodiversity footprint with other environmental and socioeconomic indicators

To analyze the interdependencies among the indicators assessed in Section 4.2, the marginal biodiversity, carbon, and water footprints have been represented together with the impact on human health and the FOB price per t soy-eq. at the state level (Figure 9). It must be noted that is not included in Figure 9, as its exceptionally high terrestrial biodiversity footprint result conceals the results visualization of the other states. The analysis shows that, from the producers' perspective, a large biodiversity footprint is not always associated with a large

deforestation area. Even though terrestrial biodiversity loss is directly correlated with land transformation (LUC) and occupation (LU), the deforested area implies the prevalence of land transformation versus occupation. For instance, while Piauí shows the highest biodiversity footprint intensity after Roraima, the soy it exported in 2022 is associated with a moderate deforestation intensity (ca. 2 ha/t soy-eq.), which also translates into a relatively low carbon footprint (<0.9 t CO₂eq/t soy-eq.). This is because, as commented above, land occupation prevails over land transformation (i.e., deforestation) for soy production in that state. On the contrary, soy exports in Rio Grande do Sul and Maranhão are linked to large deforestation areas, which translates into relatively large biodiversity and carbon footprints, as shown in Sections 4.1.1 and 4.1.2. The largest carbon footprint is, however, found in the state of Pará, in which deforestation involves tropical forest loss, the most carbon-rich biome. It must be noted that the carbon footprint is not only driven by LUC but also the other stages, mainly soybean farming and fertilizers production, which explains the relatively large carbon footprints in states such as Mato Grosso, Mato Grosso do Sul, or Goiás. Since the main contributor to the carbon and water footprints and human health impacts is the production and application of fertilizers, as explained in Section 4.1, the three indicators are positively correlated in these states in the Centre-West. These are leading soy-producing states with high processing capacities, which also export a large share of soy derivatives. This implies a relatively larger contribution of the crushing to both the carbon and water footprints, as well as to the human health impacts.

As for the FOB price, differences across states are only minor, mainly driven by differences in the volume and the commodities they export (soy, oil, cake). This can be attributed to the fact that this is an international commodity whose price tends to be similar regardless of the origin. Ceará exhibits the highest price (around 600 USD/t soy.eq.) (Figure 9), showing a trade-off between the impacts and the revenues generated by soy derivatives exports. This is due to its low score on negatively oriented impacts (i.e., terrestrial biodiversity footprint, climate change, freshwater consumption, human health, and deforestation) and its strong performance in the FOB perceived price. In contrast, the states of Paraná and Maranhão exhibit the poorest economic performances. Despite not being shown in Figure 9, Roraima records the highest prices for its exports of soybean derivative products and shows favorable results for indicators other than the biodiversity impact. Finally, among the states with the largest share of the soybean export market, Mato Grosso achieved a slightly better performance than the state of Bahia in terms of FOB/t soy-eq.

Figure 9. Results of the soy indicators for the producing states of Brazil in 2022. The state of Roraima is not plotted due to its large biodiversity footprint.

From the perspective of importing countries (Figure 10), it becomes more challenging to identify interdependencies across the indicators assessed, since a country can ultimately import soybean derivatives from different producing municipalities in Brazil, which are the most important driver of impacts. Nevertheless, it can be noted that soybeans exported to Belgium, Ireland, and Spain exhibit less negative overall performance on the indicators, whereas those exported to Germany show less favorable results. Notably, both Spain and Germany have a significant share in the European market for Brazilian soybeans (19.8% and 9.6% in 2022, respectively). Meanwhile, France and the Netherlands, which also play a key role in this market, show an overall performance close to the average. Instead, Portugal, whose imports come mainly from Roraima, the state with the largest marginal biodiversity footprint, is also the country associated with the greatest deforestation, while it shows relatively lower carbon and water footprints and human health impact.

Figure 10. Results of the soy indicators for the importing EU countries in 2022.

Although Figures 9 and 10 help assess interdependencies between indicators to validate and quantify the magnitude of the observed correlations, the Spearman correlation coefficient is also estimated in Table 3. The results confirm the strong direct correlation identified in the figures and further reveal a relevant relationship between soy product prices and the impacts on carbon footprint, freshwater consumption, and human health, suggesting possible trade-offs among these indicators. Additionally, a significant negative correlation is observed between soy product prices and terrestrial biodiversity footprint, indicating this impact is not considered in the product pricing. This suggests an economic model based on low prices, supported by the failure to account for the environmental costs associated with biodiversity loss.

Table 3. Spearman rank correlation coefficient for terrestrial biodiversity footprint, Carbon footprint, Freshwater footprint, Damage to human health, Deforestation (DFR) and soy products price.

	Carbon footprint	Freshwater footprint	Damage on human health	Deforestation	Perceived price of soy products
Terrestrial biodiversity footprint	0.05	-0.03	-0.02	0.07	-0.23
Carbon footprint		0.85	0.96	0.03	0.19
Freshwater footprint			0.9	-0.03	0.30
Damage to human health				-0.04	0.22
Deforestation					0.04

4.4 Implementation in GLOBIOM

The value of indicators mentioned in section 3.2 projected for the 'business-as-usual' scenario SSP2 are presented in this section. It should be noted that the calibration of the model is still in process, and the trends presented in this deliverable should be interpreted as preliminary. They, however, provide an illustration of the information that the chosen indicators can provide in upcoming deliverables' projections for WP7.

4.4.1. Socioeconomic impacts

4.4.1.1 Socioeconomic impacts globally

Food availability

As illustrated in Figure 11, food availability projections differ across regions in terms of total value and composition (between plant-based and animal-based products) both by 2020 and in terms of trends to 2050. Food availability is in general lower in 2020, with a lower proportion of animal-based products, in regions like Africa and the Middle East (AME) and South Asia (SAS), as compared to regions like Northern America (NAM), Latin and Central America (OAM, including Brazil BRA) and Rest of the world (ROW, including European Union EUE). In the business-as-usual scenario SSP2, food availability is expected to increase by 2050 for all regions but more strongly for the AME, SAS, and OAM than other regions.

Figure 11. Projected trends in food availability per capita (in energetic content, kcal/cap/day) for five world regions (Northern America NAM, Latin and Central America OAM, Africa and Middle East AME, South Asia SAS, Rest of the World ROW) and two zoomed regions (Brazil BRA and European Union EUE). The colors differentiate animal-based (turquoise) vs plant-based food products (yellow).

Production and net trade

As seen in Figure 12, the projections of future levels of production and net trade allow the main players in soy-related supply chains to be understood. Focusing on different products or groups of products provides different insights:

- **Livestock products (LSP):** Overall, as compared to crop-based products, the model projects a relatively limited trade. AME is the only region with a large and increasing import dependency, while SAS switches from a slight import dependency in 2020 to a slight net exporter position by 2050. OAM (including BRA) and ROW (including EUE) will consolidate their position as net exporters from 2020 to 2050. Regions with large growth in production (e.g., SAS) are expected to drive future increases in protein meal use, either domestically produced (from crushing of either imported or domestically produced soy) or imported.
- **Soy crop (SOY), Soy oil (SoyO) and Soy protein meal (SoyProM):** NAM (including the USA) and OAM (including Brazil) are the dominant producers and exporters in 2020 and further consolidate these positions until 2050. BRA is projected to generate more than half of OAM exports, increase its export levels from slightly less than 100 million tons in 2020 to more than 190 million tons by 2050, and remain the largest exporter of Soy (closely followed by NAM, also increasing its exports levels). BRA and NAM are also projected to increase or maintain their export levels for soy oil and soy protein meals, AME is projected to maintain a net importer position for soy oil, while SAS is projected to become a net importer of soy oil and remain a net importer of soy protein meal, while becoming the largest producer of these two commodities, mostly through the crushing of soy imports. ROW (and EUE) remain a net importer of soy protein meal and exporter of soy oil.
- **Other crops (OCROP), protein meals (OProM) and vegetable oils (OVegO):** projected production and net trade patterns differ from that of soy-based products in several ways. For example, SAS is projected develop a net exporter position (except for other protein meals), while ROW (and EUE) is projected to remain a net importer of other vegetable oils.

Figure 12. Projected trends in production and net trade (physical volume, in million tons of fresh matter) for five world regions (Northern America NAM, Latin and Central America OAM, Africa and Middle East AME, South Asia SAS, Rest of the World ROW) and two zoomed regions (Brazil BRA and European Union EUE). The colors differentiate livestock products (LSP, in turquoise) from soy (SOY, in purple) and other primary crops (OCRP, in yellow), soy oil (SOyO, in red) from other vegetable oils (OVeGo, in orange), and soy protein meals (SOyProM, in blue) from other protein meals (OProM, in green).

Value of production

The projected value of production (USD 2000) for primary agricultural products (i.e., excluding secondary products such as vegetable oils and protein meals) is displayed in Figure 13, based on producer prices, and allows an understanding of how the value of production differs from the physical volume of production.

First, the relative contribution of various product groups (soy crop SOY; other crops OCROP; livestock products LSP) to the total value of production is different from their contribution to total physical production volume. For example, livestock products are often projected to represent a larger share in value of production than in physical production, due to relatively higher market prices. Although BRA remains the largest producer and exporter of soy, this activity represents less than a quarter of the value of production from all crops and less than the value of livestock production.

Second, the extent to which changes in production levels translate into changes in production value is moderated by changes in market price levels. For example, despite a projected increase in physical production volume by 22% from 2020 to 2030, the value of soy crop production in NAM is projected to decrease over the same period, because of a projected price decrease. For similar reasons, the increases in the production of livestock products projected in SAS over 2020-2050 lead to proportionally lower increases in the value of livestock production.

Figure 13. Projected trends in value of production (in billions of USD2000) for five world regions (Northern America NAM, Latin and Central America OAM, Africa and Middle East AME, South Asia SAS, Rest of the World ROW) and two zoomed regions (Brazil BRA and European Union EUE). The colors differentiate livestock products (turquoise, LSP) from soy (purple, SOY) and other primary crops (yellow, OCROP).

4.4.1.1 Socioeconomic impacts in Brazil

Crop production

At the biome level in 2020, the Cerrado and Mata Atlantica biomes host 90% of the total Brazilian crop production. Regarding soy production, almost 60% of the production takes place in the Cerrado biome in 2020. In Amazonia, the production is dominated by corn production. At the state level, Minas Gerais, São Paulo and Pernambuco show a predominance of sugarcane production, whereas soy and corn are mostly produced in Mato Grosso and Paraná. We observe an increase in production in all biomes except in São Paulo, where production decreases from 2030 onwards. In the Cerrado biome, more specifically in the state of Goiás, an increase in corn production associated with a decrease in sugarcane production can be observed.

Figure 14: Projected trends in crop production (in 1000 tons of fresh matter) for the six Brazilian biomes and for the seven States with the highest impact, and split between the six main crops (Cassava – Cass, Corn – Corn, Rice – Rice, Soy – Soya, Sugarcane – SugC, Wheat – Whea)

4.4.2. Environmental impacts

4.4.2.1 Impacts from agricultural production globally

Land use:

As displayed in Figure 15, the projected changes in land use from 2020 to 2050 vary across regions, with relatively stable land use in NAM and ROW (including EUE) and further conversion of forest and other land to cropland and pasture in other regions (OAM, AME, SAS). This is an expected pattern for SSP2 (e.g., Fricko et al., 2017; Stehfest et al., 2019), with proportionally lower increases in total cropland than increases in total production due to projected yield increases (see also CLEVER deliverable D6.3). OAM, and more particularly BRA, is projected to have a relatively high and increasing share of dedicated to soy (including both single cropping and soy-corn double cropping), and a relatively high forest loss rate.

Figure 15. Projected trends in land use (in million hectares) for five world regions (Northern America NAM, Latin and Central America OAM, Africa and Middle East AME, South Asia SAS, Rest of the World ROW) and two zoomed regions (Brazil BRA and European Union EUE). The colors differentiate pasture (turquoise) from soy crop physical area (purple) and other primary crop physical area (yellow), as well as forest (red) and other land (blue).

Water use:

The projected changes in water use for irrigated crop production are displayed in Figure 16. For most regions, irrigation water use is projected to remain stable or slightly increase, with projected increases in water use efficiency mitigating the projected increases in irrigated crop production (see also deliverable D6.3). The projected water use associated with soy production

varies across regions, with no impact in OAM (including in BRA), and a significant and increasing share of total water use in NAM.

Figure 16. Projected trends in water use for irrigation (in km³) for five world regions (Northern America NAM, Latin and Central America OAM, Africa and Middle East AME, South Asia SAS, Rest of the World (ROW) and two zoomed regions (Brazil BRA and European Union EUE). The colors differentiate soy crops (purple) from other crops (yellow).

GHG emissions:

As displayed in Figure 17, projected GHG emissions from agriculture and LUC also vary across regions. By 2020, livestock emissions dominate in some aggregated regions (e.g., NAM, ROW – including EUE –, SAS), while LUC emissions dominate in others (e.g., OAM – including BRA –, AME), and crop emissions represent a marginal share in OAM & AME. Soy represents a small share of crop emissions, except in BRA. Over 2020-2050, LUC emissions are projected to remain stable (when low in 2020) or decrease (when high in 2020), while crop and livestock production emissions are projected to increase globally.

Figure 17. Projected trends in annual GHG emissions (in billion tons of CO₂ equivalents per year) from the agriculture and land use (AFOLU) sectors for five world regions (Northern America NAM, Latin and Central America OAM, Africa and Middle East AME, South Asia SAS, Rest of the World ROW) and two zoomed regions (Brazil BRA and European Union EUE). The colors differentiate emissions from livestock production (turquoise, LSP), soy crop production (purple), other crop production (yellow), and land use change (red).

Biodiversity impacts from local agricultural production:

As displayed in Figure 18, the projected biodiversity impacts on terrestrial ecosystems from local agricultural production vary across regions by 2020 and 2050. They are, in absolute terms, higher in regions with a significant share of tropical ecosystems (e.g., OAM, AME, and SAS, as compared to NAM and ROW). While the relative weight of land transformation is higher in regions of larger LUC (e.g., OAM, AME, SAS), it decreases over time. Land occupation and climate impacts are relatively stable over time, and land occupation remains the largest impact in all regions. Climate impact is often the lowest impact, although it can be higher than land transformation (e.g., in NAM from 2020 onwards, and in ROW after 2030).

Figure 18. Projected trends in biodiversity impacts on terrestrial ecosystems (in PDF-year) from local production for five world regions (Northern America NAM, Latin and Central America OAM, Africa and Middle East AME, South Asia SAS, Rest of the World ROW) and two zoomed regions (Brazil BRA and European Union EUE). The colors differentiate impacts through climate change (blue), land occupation (red), and land transformation (green).

As displayed in Figure 19, the projected biodiversity impacts from local production on freshwater ecosystems also differ across regions. However, in absolute terms is highest in NAM and ROW, rather than in tropical regions. In terms of pressures, impacts are dominated by water stress, followed by eutrophication and then climate change. However, climate change impacts than eutrophication in EUE, while eutrophication impacts dominate in BRA. Over 2020-2050, impacts are projected to either remain stable (e.g., NAM, ROW), increase (OAM, SAS), or decrease (AME, where water consumption is expected to decrease, leading to lower water stress).

Figure 19. Projected trends in biodiversity impacts on freshwater ecosystems (in PDF-year) from local production for five world regions (Northern America NAM, Latin and Central America OAM, Africa and Middle East AME, South Asia SAS, Rest of the World ROW) and two zoomed regions (Brazil BRA and European Union EUE). The colors differentiate impacts through climate change (blue), land occupation (red), and land transformation (green).

4.4.2.2 Impacts from agricultural production in Brazil

Climate change:

As seen in Figure 20, GHG emissions related to agricultural production occur mainly in Amazonia and Cerrado regions. In those biomes associated with high deforestation, climate change impact is mainly due to LUC emissions (Camara et al., 2015), whereas, in other biomes, other agricultural emissions are driving the impact. When looking at future trends, the pressure in the Amazonia seems to be increasing in SSP2, whereas it decreases in the Cerrado and well as in most of the other biomes. Other agricultural emissions, on the other hand, increase or are relatively stable in most biomes.

Similar trends can be observed at the State level, with LUC emissions dominating in states located in the Amazonia and Cerrado biomes, such as the states of Pará and Mato Grosso. While total GHG emissions show an overall decrease until 2050 (Figure 17), the state of Pará, in Amazonia, shows an increase in emissions until 2040, before slightly decreasing.

Figure 20. Projected trends in greenhouse gas emissions (in million tons of CO₂eq, Mt CO₂eq) for the six Brazilian biomes and for the seven States with the highest impact and split between land use change emissions (blue), and other agricultural emissions (yellow).

Land use:

Regarding land occupation, Figure 21 shows that forest area, predominantly located in Amazonia, decrease between 2020 and 2050 in SSP2, while pasture area increases. Cropland expansion can be observed mostly in the Cerrado biome, as well as in Pampa replacing respectively forest and pasture. At the state level, similarly to what has been observed previously, forest coverage loss is predominantly in the states of Amazonas and Pará, major states of the Amazonia biome. However, it can here be noticed that a large share of the deforestation happens in the State of Para. Cropland expansion over pasture can be observed in the states of Goiás, Mato Grosso, and Mato Grosso do Sul, which are major agricultural states, particularly for soybean production (Figure 15).

Figure 21. Projected trends in land use (in 1000 ha) for the six Brazilian biomes and the eight largest states, differentiated between the different land uses covered in GLOBIOM (Cropland, Forest, Other natural land and Pasture).

Water consumption:

As shown in Figure 22 below, water consumption due to agriculture in Brazil mainly comes from the cultivation of sugarcane and wheat. Since 85% of the Sugarcane production is located in the southern region of Brazil, and 50% is in Sao Paulo state (Cerrado and Mata Atlantica biomes), it's also where more of the water consumption occurs (Scarpore et al., 2016). The increase in water consumption between 2020 and 2050 occurs primarily in the state of Paraná for the cultivation of wheat and in Sao Paulo for the cultivation of Sugarcane. In other biomes or states, we observe that the water demand is mainly due to the cultivation of rice.

Figure 22. Projected trends in Water consumption (water for irrigation, in km3) for the two largest Brazilian states, and biomes and split between the different irrigated crops covered in GLOBIOM. (Cassava – Cass, Cotton – Cott, Potato – Pota, Rapeseed – Rape, Rice – Rice, Sorghum – Srgh, Sugarcane – SugC, Sunflower – Sunf, Sweet Potato – SwPo, Wheat – Whea).

Biodiversity impact from local production:

As shown in Figure 23, terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems are most affected by human activities in Mata Atlantica, Cerrado, and Amazonia. The largest pressure on freshwater ecosystems in most biomes is freshwater eutrophication, as well as climate change, in biomes where most LUC happens, such as Amazonia. Similarly, the largest pressure on terrestrial ecosystems is land occupation, as well as land transformation, where applicable. The evolution of the impact on freshwater ecosystems increases in the most impacted biomes, while it tends to decrease in other biomes. On terrestrial ecosystems, impact decreases following a decrease in LUC in most biomes. At the state level, it can be noticed that in the state of Sao Paulo, a major pressure on freshwater ecosystems is water consumption, mainly due to sugarcane cultivation, as previously observed (see Figure 16)

Figure 23. Projected trends in biodiversity impact (Potentially disappeared fraction, PDF.y) for the four biomes and five states with the highest impact, and split between the different pressures covered in GLOBIOM, and affected ecosystem type (freshwater or terrestrial).

4.4.2.3 Additional impacts from upstream and downstream for Brazil soy supply chains

In section 4.4.2.1-2, projected environmental impacts of Brazilian agricultural activities have been illustrated, based on the outcome of GLOBIOM for the SSP2 scenario. However as previously stated, parts of the supply chain of agricultural products are missing in GLOBIOM, the model primarily covering the impact of direct farming activities and related changes in resource use. Based on the results of the LCA from Section 4.1, we expanded the model to include upstream and downstream supply chain impacts of soy production in Brazil (see methods in Section 3.2). In this section, the additional impacts from these supply chain steps are presented and compared to the footprint from farming previously presented.

Figure 24 displays the total impact of soy production in Brazil per biome and differentiates the different supply chain steps (*Farming, Processing, Domestic transport, International transport*) for different impact categories. To align with results in Section 4.1, the same supply chain steps are shown, with an additional split between farming impacts that were already covered by GLOBIOM (*Farming - GLOBIOM*), and additional ones (*Farming - Other impacts*).

Figure 24. Soy supply chain impacts in the different biomes and for the different midpoints (climate change and freshwater consumption) and endpoints (aquatic ecosystems, terrestrial ecosystems) covered in GLOBIOM in 2020, and differentiated per supply chain steps. Farming impacts are further differentiated between impacts already covered in GLOBIOM (*Farming - GLOBIOM*) and additional impacts (*Farming - other impacts*)

As shown in Figure 24, in most regions, farming impacts, including impacts already accounted for by GLOBIOM (*Farming - GLOBIOM*), as well as additional farming impacts from LCA (*Farming - other impacts*), account for the largest share of the impact of soy commodities production for all impact categories. However, for Climate change as well as Freshwater consumption midpoint impacts, the share of additional impacts, newly calculated based on the LCA results, is predominant. In the case of freshwater consumption, the impact comes even entirely from additional supply chain steps, primarily input production (*e.g., fertilizer production*, included in *Farming - other*). Lastly, when considering endpoint impacts on terrestrial ecosystems, the

share of additional impacts is much smaller since land use and LUC are the main drivers, whereas, for aquatic ecosystems, the results are a bit more contrasted.

In absolute terms, the impacts of climate change, freshwater consumption, and aquatic ecosystem damage are directly correlated with the volume of soy derivatives exported, as these depend on the emissions released and inputs consumed throughout the supply chains originating from each state. In contrast, as for terrestrial ecosystem damage, both Mata Atlantica and Cerrado clearly show much higher impacts due to associated LUC and biodiversity richness. The Cerrado clearly dominates in all impact categories, followed by the Mata Atlantica and to some extent, Amazonia. In contrast, the impacts in the Pampa and Pantanal are relatively minor. It's also interesting to note that, when looking at climate change and water consumption alone, the Cerrado is the clear hotspot with the highest impacts, nearly twice as high as Mata Atlantica; however, when considering terrestrial biodiversity, the Mata Atlantica shows almost the same level of impacts than the Cerrado. This highlights the importance of considering both midpoint and endpoint indicators to capture the full extent of environmental impacts. The spatial distribution of impacts from supply chain steps beyond farming should, however, be interpreted with caution, as it is strongly influenced by how they are modeled in GLOBIOM. Currently, all impacts are allocated to the producing region, even though input production, crushing, and, most notably, transport occur in other areas. This perspective reflects the environmental footprint of the soy supply chain from the producer's standpoint (including the entire value chain). It's also important to remember that domestic transport might be underestimated since LCA results did not include transport emissions associated with the domestic market.

The integration into GLOBIOM also allowed us to put these impacts into perspective by comparing them to the previously calculated Brazilian footprint (Figure 25). The impact of soy production, including all supply chain steps, accounts for 17% of the Brazilian climate change and terrestrial biodiversity footprint, but only 1.8% of the total freshwater consumption. GHG emissions associated with other supply chain steps for soy alone account for 75% of the soy emissions and almost 15% of the total emissions from Brazilian soy derivative exports. While this may seem relatively small, this highlights the importance of considering additional supply chain impacts in GLOBIOM, as including those of other crops could further increase the overall environmental footprint. However, it is important to note that not all emissions should be included in the territorial Brazilian footprint, as not all supply chain steps occur within Brazil (e.g. transport emissions or impacts of input production).

Figure 25. Soy production compared to Brazilian footprint. In Yellow, described as “Farming - GLOBIOM” includes all already calculated impacts from GLOBIOM, which are related to direct agricultural and forestry activities.

When looking at the evolution of the biodiversity impact of the production of soy commodities over time in Brazil (Figure 26), we observe a decline in impact on terrestrial ecosystems, due to a decrease in farming impacts, more specifically in land transformation impacts, while the impact on aquatic ecosystem increases, due to an increase in supply chain impacts, more specifically GHG emissions. Over time, there is a noticeable shift in the distribution of freshwater ecosystem impacts, as well as climate change impact, with the share attributed to non-farming supply chain stages increasing while farming-related impacts decline. This is likely influenced by the fact that the LCA coefficients used do not evolve dynamically with the scenarios in GLOBIOM, which could potentially lead to an overestimation of the impacts in the projections. In contrast, the impacts on terrestrial ecosystems, primarily driven by farming, closely follow the trends observed for Brazil as a whole.

Figure 26. Evolution of the mid-point impacts (climate change and freshwater consumption) and end-point impacts (freshwater and terrestrial biodiversity) of the soy supply chain over time, differentiated per supply chain step.

4.4.3. Comparison with attributional LCA results

This section compares the environmental impact results for all soy production destined to EU exports (per ton of soy-eq.) obtained under the attributional LCA (ALCA) approach described in Section 3.1 and the consequential LCA (CLCA) approach developed by integrating impact coefficients into GLOBIOM, as described in section 3.2. Figure 27 shows the level of soy production for exports to the EU, as well as mid-point (freshwater consumption, climate change)

and endpoint (terrestrial and freshwater biodiversity impacts) environmental impacts of Brazilian states only for the farming stage, for which the two approaches differ the most. For the other supply chain stages, the CLCA approach relies more directly on the ALCA estimations, and the two estimates do not differ (see section 3.2.1).

While the ALCA results show values for the year 2022 (assessed in this deliverable) in the y-axis, the CLCA results show GLOBIOM outcomes for the year 2020 in the x-axis, the closest decadal time step available in the simulation period. The comparison illustrates the total impacts per state associated with soy production for export to the EU. Since GLOBIOM results reflect the impacts of total soy production in Brazil, only a proportion of these impacts is considered, corresponding to the share of soy exports to the EU as represented in GLOBIOM. It should be noted that at this stage, differences across states in the fate of soy production (e.g., the share of production processed and exported to various countries or domestically produced) are not explicitly modeled in GLOBIOM to the difference of the ALCA approach. Therefore, for CLCA estimates, the state-level soy production destined for EU exports is simply obtained by multiplying state-level production by the share of Brazil's total soy production exported to the EU.

Figure 27. Comparison at the state level of the impacts of soy exports to the EU (in absolute terms) as well as production of soy for the EU, according to GLOBIOM estimations (CLCA) in 2020 and ALCA estimations from section 4.3.1. in 2022. The 1:1 reference line (black) represents perfect agreement between the two approaches, with the R^2 value indicating the correlation strength.

The two approaches deliver results with the same order of magnitude. We can observe a correlation between the two sets of results across impact categories, especially towards the lowest values of the distributions, where most of the states fall (bottom-left quarter). The two states of Bahia and Mato Grosso, consistently appear as exceptions across impact categories and production numbers, where ALCA delivers much higher results than CLCA. As for climate change, six states show higher values with ALCA than with CLCA, with the most difference being observed in the State of Bahia (ALCA estimates more than 4 Mt CO₂eq associated with the production of soy for exports to EU, while GLOBIOM estimates less than 1Mt CO₂eq). For freshwater consumption, most of the states show lower values in CLCA than in ALCA, with the three states of Tocantins, Piaui, and Minas Gerais showing more similar values between the two approaches. Finally, biodiversity impacts have the lowest correlation, with most states showing higher biodiversity impacts in GLOBIOM than in ALCA, with, for example, the state of Minas Gerais resulting in 6 times more impacts on terrestrial biodiversity according to GLOBIOM than according to ALCA.

These differences can be related to various methodological differences, namely:

- **Reference year:** ALCA is calculated for the year 2022, and GLOBIOM uses 2020 for the CLCA results. This translates into differences in the volume of soybeans produced as well as differences in underlying LUC.
- **Volume of soybean produced and destined to EU exports:** although GLOBIOM used the impact coefficients per ton of soy-eq. from the ALCA approach, both the quantity of soybeans produced and the share of production exported to the EU may be different than the one in TRASE. Although we observe a positive correlation between the total quantity of soybeans produced (Figure 27, R₂ = 0.6), there are deviations across states (e.g., Bahia), and these also seem to be responsible for similar differences in mid- and end-point impact differences. It must be noted that the ALCA approach had to assume the municipality of origin for unknown flows.
- **Land Use Change (LUC):** ALCA measures direct LUC according to the approach detailed in section 3.1, based on observed land areas across uses, while GLOBIOM provides modeled LUC.
- **Biodiversity model:** ALCA used Scherer et al (2023) for calculating terrestrial biodiversity impact related to land use, and LC-IMPACT for other impact categories. GLOBIOM used LC-IMPACT for all categories.
- **Spatial resolution:** GLOBIOM operates at the simulation unit level which does not correspond exactly to the shape of Brazilian municipalities.

This comparison highlights that differences should be expected when looking at the direct farming impacts and that for increased accuracy of CLCA estimates, it may be worth improving the state-level trends in soy production and exploring the potential to model more explicitly state-level differences in the fate of production. However, the latter must be viewed from a system dynamic perspective, through which patterns observed in 2020 may change in the future, depending on the stickiness of the subnational supply chain structure.

For other LCA stages, discrepancies are expected, namely:

- **Processing:** ALCA only considers crushing in Brazil for exports, while GLOBIOM also considers crushing for domestic consumption
- **Domestic trade:** ALCA estimates transport routes based on a cost-minimization problem, while since GLOBIOM currently lacks information regarding subnational resolution of trade, the subnational distribution of soy exports flows from Trase and COMEX-stat has been used. This means that the subnational distribution of the crushing and transport impacts is not directly linked to the distribution of soy production as estimated by GLOBIOM. This would need to be refined in a later version to better represent subnational trade and could increase the differences between the two estimations.
- **International trade:** ALCA uses observed bilateral trade flows based on data from Trase while GLOBIOM simulates international trade based on commodity price changes.

CONCLUSIONS

Soybeans from Brazil are assessed as an example of one of the most internationally traded products, largely associated with LUC, deforestation, and subsequent biodiversity loss in the last decades. Soybean exports also imply the displacement of other environmental and socioeconomic impacts along global supply chains, from producers to consumers. This deliverable derives quantitative indicators on the environmental and socioeconomic impacts of Brazilian soy exports by combining detailed trade data and LCA approaches. The indicators assess trade-offs between biodiversity loss and other sustainability dimensions along the whole supply chain. The indicators were subsequently integrated into the global modeling framework GLOBIOM to enable the generation of long-term, scenario-specific projections of environmental and socioeconomic impacts from agricultural and forest activities, as illustrated in this deliverable with a business-as-usual scenario (SSP2).

The LCA impacts of soybean derivative exports from Brazil are strongly influenced by the municipality of origin, as it determines the impact intensity of key contributing stages. In particular, land occupation and transformation significantly affect the biodiversity footprint; however, the biodiversity footprint is related to the deforestation index only when land transformation prevails over land occupation. The production of agricultural inputs, especially fertilizers, plays a major role in the carbon footprint, water consumption, and damage to human health. As a result, a strong interdependence among these three indicators is observed. Additionally, trade-offs are evidenced between these three indicators and FOB prices of soybean commodities. However, biodiversity loss exhibits an inverse correlation with lower FOB prices, suggesting that such pricing dynamics may be leveraged by the failure to internalize the environmental costs associated with biodiversity depletion. Rather than constituting a definitive and generalizable conclusion, these findings can serve as a starting point for more in-depth studies on the interdependence patterns between negative environmental impacts and the economic benefits generated by the Brazilian soybean market, which can help organizations and decision-makers make informed choices that promote sustainable commodity trade.

At the global to Brazilian state level, the analysis of GLOBIOM estimates showed high variation in environmental impacts and socioeconomic performance indicators. This demonstrates the ability of the modeling framework to explore synergies and trade-offs across social and environmental goals, and across multiple locations and supply stage stages (e.g., from production to consumption). Across biomes in Brazil, the Amazon, Cerrado, and Mata Atlantica consistently ranked among the most affected biomes. In the case of freshwater consumption, the states of São Paulo and Paraná account for 85% of the impact. In contrast, their contribution to other impact categories, such as climate change or land use, is lower. The linkage between GLOBIOM and the impact coefficients from LCA showed the importance of taking into consideration in GLOBIOM the supply chain steps beyond farm production, especially when it comes to climate change impacts and water use. However, the methodology still requires some refining, for example regarding the subnational distribution of trade flows, and therefore also impacts associated with downstream supply chains: in the current methodology, the subnational distribution from *Trase* combined with COMEX-Stat is used and applied to the total

Brazilian trade flows. Additionally, due to lack of dedicated LCA data, the analysis does not account for domestic transportation related to domestic consumption, nor does it include the impacts of processing activities occurring outside Brazil or secondary transport in cases of re-export. Finally, the impact coefficients used remain static across different scenarios and time steps, which may lead to over- or underestimations in future projections.

PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED

- Environmental footprints of soybean exports to the EU, from producer and consumer perspective
- Socioeconomic indicators for soybean exports to the EU
- Indirect environmental and socioeconomic impacts when considering market-mediated effects
- Long-term projections of impacts

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